

inoculant which contained approximately 10^8 cells/g of peat soil carrier, following the recommended seed treatment method. After sprouting, the soaked seeds were sown in the nursery bed and 2 kg *Azospirillum* biofertilizer mixed with 25 kg powdered farmyard manure (FYM) was broadcast. In the main field, 2 kg *Azospirillum* biofertilizer mixed with 25 kg of powdered FYM/ha was broadcast before transplanting. The roots of 25-d-old rice seedlings were dipped in a water-slurry of 1 kg *Azospirillum* for 20 min before transplanting in 16-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Tillers and dry weight were recorded 60 d after transplanting, and grain and straw yields at harvest.

Tillering was enhanced by increased fertilizer N (Table 1) and *Azospirillum* biofertilizer significantly increased tiller numbers and plant dry weight at all fertilizer levels. Maximum increase in plant dry weight was with 50% fertilizer N.

Azospirillum biofertilizer treatment markedly increased the grain and straw yields at all N levels (Table 2). Grain yield response to *Azospirillum* biofertilizer was more pronounced at lower levels of fertilizer N (0 and 50%). Significant increases in tiller numbers, plant dry weight, and grain yield also were obtained at 100% N level with *Azospirillum* treatment, indicating that the higher level of fertilizer N (75 kg N/ha) did not inhibit activity of the *Azospirillum* strain. The mean grain yield at 50% N fertilizer level with *Azospirillum* treatment equaled yield with 100% N fertilizer alone.

Effect of combining chemical N and *Sesbania aculeata* in upland rice

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The lateritic sandy-loam upland soils of Bhubaneswar are low in organic

Table 1. Effect of *Azospirillum* biofertilizer on tillering and dry weight of irrigated IR50 at Madurai, India.^a

Fertilizer level	Tillers/plant (no.)		Dry wt (g/plant)	
	No <i>Azospirillum</i>	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculant at 6 kg/ha	No <i>Azospirillum</i>	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculant
No N	12.0	15.0	10.3	11.8
50% N	14.7	16.1	11.0	13.9
15% N	15.3	19.0	13.2	14.9
100% N	11.3	20.1	14.5	15.5
CD (P = 0.05%)	1.6	1.6	0.03	0.03

^a Means of 9 observations.

Table 2. Influence of *Azospirillum* biofertilizer on grain and straw yields of irrigated and rainfed upland rice, Madurai, India.

Fertilizer level	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)	Straw yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)
	Untreated	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculated		Untreated	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculated	
<i>Irrigated (IR50)</i>						
No N	2.1	3.2	47.1	5.6	5.8	3.6
50% N	3.3	4.1	24.5	6.6	7.7	20.6
15% N	3.2	4.4	17.6	7.1	8.3	16.1
100% N	4.2	5.2	22.7	8.7	9.8	2.6
CD (P = 0.05)	0.2	0.2		0.156	0.156	
<i>Rainfed upland (PMK. 1)</i>						
No N	2.0	2.2	15.4	2.5	3.4	43.4
50% N	2.3	2.9	25.9	3.6	4.6	21.4
75% N	2.4	2.9	18.0	4.0	4.8	20.4
100% N	2.9	3.1	6.0	4.9	5.8	18.8
CD (P = 0.05%)	0.04	0.04		0.1	0.1	

The rainfed upland experiment was in a rainfed banded field at Paramakudi. With rice starch solution as adhesive, seeds of PMK. 1 were coated with *Azospirillum* biofertilizer at 1 kg peat-based inoculant/75 kg seeds per ha. In addition, 2 kg biofertilizer/ha was mixed with 15 kg dry powdered FYM and broadcast in the main field before direct seeding. Three levels of fertilizer N in the form

of urea were applied.

Maximum increase in grain yield due to *Azospirillum* biofertilizer treatment was with the 50% N level (20 kg N/ha) (Table 2). Grain yield at this level equaled that with full fertilizer N, *Azospirillum* biofertilizer enhanced straw yield at all N levels; the maximum increase was at zero-N level. □

matter (0.43 to 0.5% C), base status (CEC 3.8-4.1 meq/100 g soil), pH (5.1 to 5.4), and available P (14 kg/ha, Bray's) and high in Fe and Al. But farmers rarely use farmyard manure or compost because the manures are diverted to produce rice in low and medium lands. Moreover, farmers hesitate to grow a green manure crop in lieu of a kharif crop.

During 1985-86 kharif, upland rice

Subhadra was sown at 100 kg/ha in 15- × 10-cm rows with and without *Sesbania aculeata* broadcast at 40 kg seed/ha with 4 N levels. Half the N was applied at sowing, half at tillering. All treatments received a basal 13 kg P and 25 kg K/ha.

At 20 d after germination, sesbania plants were killed by spraying 0.9% propanil. The leaves and the stems created a temporary mulch that

automatically disintegrated and mixed with the soil within a week. No manual mixing was necessary and there was no sign of injury to the rice crop.

The legume increased rice germination by 21% under the crust and affected the lateritic upland situation. Twenty-day-old sesbania bearing 7 to 17 nodules/plant contributed 4.3-6.3 t green manure/ha.

Grain yield increased significantly (see table). The yield with sesbania alone equaled yield with 40 kg N/ha. □

Effects of nitrogen and sesbania on number of nodules, green matter from sesbania, plant population, and rice yield. Orissa, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Sesbania nodules/plant ^a (no.)	Sesbania green matter incorporated (t/ha) ^a	Rice plants/m ²		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Without sesbania	With sesbania	Without sesbania	With sesbania
0	6.8	4.3	274	326	1.1	1.4
20	12.8	4.8	277	241	1.2	1.5
30	13.2	5.6	218	345	1.3	1.5
40	15.6	5.8	252	313	1.5	1.8
50	17.0	6.3	280	359	1.6	2.1
Mean	13.10	5.4	260	316	1.3	1.6
CD (0.05)						0.2

^aTreatments had received 50% N at time of data collection.

Split application of slow-release urea

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We studied the comparative efficiency and time of application of slow-release urea materials such as neem cake-coated urea (NCCU, 20% neem cake powder), coal tar-coated urea (CTCU, 1% coal tar), urea supergranule (USG, 1-g size), and prilled urea (PU) in 2 soil types.

ADT36 (110 d, Jun-Sep 1984) and IR20 (135 d, Sep 1984-Feb 1985) were tested in the clayey loam soils of Aduthurai (silty clay to clay, Vertisol, clay 40% low in N) where 2 rice crops are usually grown. IR20 (medium duration, Jul-Dec 1984) was tested in the sandy loam soils of Pattukottai (sandy loam, Alfisol, clay 12.0% low in N). The recommended NPK of 75.0-

Effect of split application of slow-release urea on yield. India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	Clay soil		Sandy loam soil
	Crop 1	Crop 2	
<i>Source</i>			
NCCU	4.6	4.6	4.6
CTCU	4.8	4.7	4.7
USG	5.0	4.7	5.0
PU	4.4	4.5	4.7
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2
<i>Time of application</i>			
Single basal (slow-release urea)	4.5	4.6	4.5
Single basal (50% slow-release + 50% PU)	4.5	4.5	4.5
Split application ^a (slow-release urea)	5.0	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal PU + topdressed slow-release urea)	4.9	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal slow-release + topdressed PU)	4.6	4.8	4.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2

^aSplit application = 50% N before planting, 50% N at maximum tillering.

37.5-37.5 kg/ha for the 110-d variety and 100-50-50 kg/ha for the 135-d variety were applied.

USG gave significantly higher yields than PU in both soil types (see table).

Yields with NCCU and CTCU only equaled that with PU. Split application of slow-release urea gave higher yields than single basal in both soils. □

Effect of soil moisture regime and straw incorporation on root growth and yield of rice

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We conducted a lysimeter experiment with rice variety PR106 on a calcareous sandy loam soil (Typic

Ustochrept). Air-dried soil was passed through a 2-mm sieve and used to fill iron barrels 1 m high with 50-cm internal diameter. The treatments, replicated 3 times, were combinations of 3 levels of straw incorporation (no straw, 1% straw, and 2% straw) and 3 soil moisture regimes (field capacity, saturation, and submergence). Straw was chopped into 2- to 4-cm pieces and mixed into the top 15 cm of soil.

The soil moisture treatments were imposed after 3 wk of continuous submergence following transplanting. To attain field capacity, 4-6 cm water was applied 24 h after infiltration of water previously applied. Saturation was 0-1.5 cm ponded water; submergence was 4-6 cm ponded water. Fertilizer was applied at 150 kg N and 13 kg P/ha.

Depth of roots was determined at